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Security Strategies As Predictors Of Safe Learning Environment In Public Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined security strategies as predictors of safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Three objectives, with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, guided the study. The study adopted a correlation research design, with a population of 5,833 teachers across 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size of 583 respondents, representing 10% of the entire population, was drawn from this group using a stratified sampling technique. The instrument of the study was a questionnaire which consisted of two sets, titled: Security Strategies Assessment Scale Questionnaire (SSASQ) and Safe Learning Environment Assessment Scale Questionnaire (SLEASQ). This instrument was validated, and its reliability was tested using the Cronbach alpha method, resulting in reliability coefficients of 0.95 and 0.84 for both set of the instrument. For data analysis, research questions were addressed using simple regression, while a t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 alpha level of significance. The study's findings revealed that security training, deployment of school security guards, and installation of security gadgets predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent. Therefore, it was concluded that security strategies predict a safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended, among other things, that school administrators should regularly invite security personnel to their schools to train school personnel on security tips that will help them manage security challenges and ensure a safe learning environment.

Keywords: School, Security Strategies, Safe Learning Environment

INTRODUCTION

Education and security have become central topics in school policy discussions, especially as concerns over school safety grow in response to recurring violent incidents. In recent years, the prioritisation of school security has been driven by targeted attacks that have prompted policymakers to revise existing safety protocols. These reforms aim to address the disturbing trend of violence that threatens the foundational role of schools as safe spaces for learning and development. Traditionally, schools are expected to be sanctuaries of knowledge and personal growth, places free from psychological and physical threats. Sadly, the increasing frequency of violent incidents has upended this expectation, as many educational institutions in Nigeria now face serious security threats. The security crisis in Nigeria has extended to schools, which are no longer immune to the nation's broader instability. The complex and

evolving nature of these threats has made it difficult to identify clear causes. However, the consequences are evident. For example, the Boko Haram insurgency led to the closure of formal education in 22 of Borno State's 27 local government areas by 2013 (Adewale, 2023). In Yobe State, by 2014, two of the three educational zones had no functional schools, forcing all remaining schools to relocate to Damaturu, the state capital. Similarly, 115 schools in Adamawa State were shut down, displacing over 285,000 students and more than 8,000 staff members (Adewale, 2023).

These attacks are not limited to schools alone. Religious centres, embassies, and cultural institutions have also suffered repeated assaults. High-profile cases such as the bombings of the Mogadishu Barracks (2010), the police headquarters (2011), the United Nations building (2011), and churches across Abuja and Suleja have all been attributed to terrorist groups. These events have heightened public anxiety and have made school safety a national concern, drawing the attention of educators, learners, parents, and policymakers. The Nigerian government is constitutionally mandated to provide security for all citizens, including ensuring that schools are safe for learners and staff. Security, in this context, refers to proactive measures taken to prevent harm, loss, or crime. In schools, this means establishing protective systems that create a safe environment conducive to teaching and learning. Given the amount of time students and teachers spend on school premises, the importance of securing these environments cannot be overstated. Despite this constitutional guarantee, attacks on schools continue to grow in scale and severity, posing a major concern for school administrators and stakeholders globally. Incidents of violence, kidnapping, terrorism, vandalism, arson, and other threats disrupt the stability of school environments. Such conditions endanger students, teachers, and staff and create climates of fear that hinder learning. In Maiduguri, for example, 12 public schools were burnt in 2012, forcing around 10,000 students out of education. In 2013, armed assailants killed over 20 students and a teacher at Baga Community Secondary School in Borno State. The abduction of over 200 schoolgirls in Chibok in April 2014 remains one of the most shocking attacks on education in Nigeria. Similarly, in February 2018, 110 students were abducted from Government Science and Technical College, Dapchi.

These incidents are not exclusive to northern Nigeria. The South-East and South-South regions also face insecurity, albeit in different forms. In the South-South, issues such as sexual abuse, cultism, bullying, and gang violence are prevalent. Rivers State, for instance, has reported increasing cases of sexual violence in schools. Other security challenges across regions include communal clashes, natural disasters, armed robbery, theft, extortion, and political unrest. As more schools become targets, the urgency to implement comprehensive security measures becomes critical. Wherever lives and property are involved, security becomes a necessity, not a luxury. The consequences of school-related violence are profound. Such incidents jeopardise the sustainability of education by violating the rights of learners and eroding public confidence in the school system. Unsafe school environments lead to poor learning outcomes and deter student participation. According to UNESCO, no nation can achieve inclusive and equitable quality education (SDG 4) if learners are subjected to violence or insecurity in school. The psychological trauma caused by these events often persists well into adulthood, affecting academic performance and mental health. For example, following the Chibok abduction, many students dropped out of school, and enrolment figures plummeted due to widespread fear among parents and children.

Security threats to schools are not always from insurgency or violence alone. According to Ajayi (2021), other forms of security risks include building collapses, fire outbreaks, and stampedes, often the result of poor infrastructure and inadequate safety planning. Tragic events such as the Kumbakonam fire in India, which killed 93 schoolchildren, and the 2020 Abule-Ado explosion in Lagos, which claimed the lives of 23 students, further highlight the need for comprehensive school safety strategies. An insecure school environment negatively affects both the quality of teaching and student engagement. Teachers working under constant threat are less effective, while students struggle to concentrate or even attend school. The emotional and psychological aftermath of violence can be long-lasting for all members of the school community. These fears, among parents, teachers, students, and school personnel, can cripple educational goals, leading to poor attendance, reduced enrolment, and a decline in interest in the teaching profession.

To foster a safe learning environment, schools must prioritise adequate security infrastructure. A secure school is one where learners feel free from threat and harm and where educational goals can be pursued without fear. Effective security management involves planning, organising, and directing school resources toward the goal of safety. School administrators must recognise that managing security is not an optional task, it is a vital responsibility that directly influences educational outcomes and the wellbeing of every learner. An effective school administrator or principal is aware of security challenges around the school, and it is expected that he or she makes efforts in creating a safe learning environment where teachers advance and students reach their utmost potential. In dealing with these security threats in order to create a safe learning environment, the educational administrator, who is the principal in the case of secondary school, is expected to be conversant and practical about security management strategies. He or she must have a functional security blueprint, in the form of administrative and curricular strategies, security programmes, policies, and measures for addressing security issues in the school premises. These security strategies may include security training, deployment of school security guards, installation of security gadgets, school environmental design, utilisation of police patrols, and school-community collaboration (Aryu, 2020; Uzuegbu-Wilson, 2019). However, in this study we shall explore security training, deployment of school security guards, installation of security gadgets.

Training of school members in safety matters is thus very important and should form part of the general annual staff training and development scheme of the school (Iloka, 2019). Iniobong (2022), posits that the school manager should involve, train and empower people by setting up a functional task committee whose membership should be based on merit, knowledge and experience and free from tribal factors, with uninterred authority but with a level of monitoring from the school manager to prevent them from becoming another source of threat. Security training in school provide new and different ways for teachers and students to avert issues or activities that poses as threat to them (Dessler, 2022). In other words, it helps them get new knowledge in dealing with security threat in order to guarantee safe learning environment. Owen (2022) asserted that there is a significant relationship between security training organised for school users and safe/conducive environment for learning. Some researchers have identified security training functions as follows: increases security skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes, improves quality of security plans and measures; increases the use of security tools in work; reduces risks, hazards and accidents, eliminates attacks, among others (Oguntimehin, 2021). The more students, teachers and other stakeholders of the school are trained regarding security, the more satisfied and confident they feel about the school learning environment. This lead to increase in productivity and profitability of the school organisation (Champathes, 2022). This was affirmed by Guest et al (2021), that the security training received by all stakeholders of the school system to a high extent predicts safe and secured learning environment, which necessitate school organisational commitment among teachers and students.

Deployment of security guards as a strategy refers to the process whereby the services of security personnel or guards are employed and deployed within and outside the school environment to help forestall any breach of security that may impede the peaceful learning environment of the school. The deployment of trained security guards can deter criminal agents from the school, and thereby stimulate a safe learning environment (Aryu, 2020). Due to the increasing school safety and school violence issues, schools across the nation have incorporated school security guards to assist with this problem. The school security guards are law enforcement officers used to prevent violence against the school. Results with regard to the effectiveness of deployment of security guards in reducing crime in schools. In a study of program success based on interviews with 18 School Resource Officers (SROs) in a southern city of California. Johnson (2019) found that crimes had decreased in high (secondary) schools and middle schools after SROs were assigned to those schools. Also, Homer and Fisher (2020) noted that the deployment of security guards in school has been associated with increased safe learning environment, thereby reducing criminal activities within the school, student cultist arrests and referrals to law enforcement.

Another strategy is the installation of security gadgets in schools. This process can be defined as the setting up of security facilities within the school environment (Aryu, 2020). It has to do with fixing and configuration of security gadgets like CCTV camera, walk-through metal detectors, explosive detectors, turnstiles, boom barriers, web security cameras, blind spots cameras, doorbell ringers, smart deadbolt, siren padlock, motion sensor smart lights, barking dog alarm, pressure doormat alarm, GPS trackers and many more. The security gadgets help to capture every activity or happening that takes place within the school. It keeps a memory of all the happenings in the school, which scares intending attackers away. Gichuhi, et al (2019) opined that the presence of these security gadgets can help capture criminal activities and also help the school management to monitor the activities that students and staff engage in within the school environment, thereby promoting effective administrative system. Also, Williams, et al (2019) reported that when there is heavy presence of security gadgets in school it positively predicts orderliness and deter criminal activities as well as violence. Also, it promotes teaching and learning process and better academic performance from the students. Ajayi (2021) reported that the installation of security gadgets in schools that are prone to attacks have significantly promoted safe environment for learning. Duncanson and Achilles (2019) affirmed that sophisticated gadgets and high-powered security personnel are major tools that can bring about new outcomes, continuity in administration of school and safe environment for access of quality education.

The task of making our schools safe is the responsibility of every stakeholder in the school. School administrators are the chief security officers of their schools. The first responsibility of the school administrators to guarantee safety of lives and properties is to bring on board all the school stakeholders (government, security personnels, the host community, non-governmental organizations, the alumni association, the religious bodies, parents, and student to find a lasting solution to unwarranted threats to a hitch free teaching and learning activities. In order to avoid the potential of targeted attacks on schools, school administrators must work closely with key stakeholders. They must also proactively implement intervention strategies to overcome learning impediments. Consequently, the principal in collaboration with other stakeholders is expected to come up with security strategies that will promote safe learning environment. Such school security strategies should be balanced, comprehensive and should consist of practical security measures, meaningful emergence preparedness planning, close partnerships with public safety agencies and the school community, prevention and intervention programs, positive school climate, and firm, fair, and consistent discipline. As the fear of violence and crime continues to permeate schools, the need for increased security becomes unavoidable. This is because a learning environment of fear, anxiety and insecurity is detrimental to students and teachers' performance and has a negative consequence on the wider school environment. Therefore, it is against this background, that this study examined the topic 'school security strategies as predictors of safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The lack of well-managed systems to support safety and security practices in schools across Nigeria has led to the prevalence of human-induced and natural hazards in school environments, as well as the violence and abuse perpetrated against students while they are present in school. In the period between 2012 and 2020, more than 700 teachers were reportedly killed in attacks, while more than 19,000 were displaced. Also, statistics revealed that 1 in every 5 of the world's out-of-school children is in Nigeria. Specifically, reports indicate that about 10.5 million children aged 5 to 14 are out of school; about 61 percent of children aged 6 to 11 attend primary school regularly, while only 35.6 per cent of children between the ages of 36 and 59 months (3 – 5 years) can access early childhood education in Nigeria.

This change in learning environment has created an imperative need for schools to identify tools, strategies and model programmes that can enhance the safety and success of all children and professionals who serve them. This is because when people are legally required to attend school, school personnel have the corresponding duty to provide children with a safe, secure and peaceful environment in which learning can occur. A situation where school members are faced with the risk of being harmed right inside

the school poses a lot of concern. These observed increasing incidences of security threats destabilize the security of the school (put at risk the safety of students, teachers, other school stakeholders) and create an environment of insecurity and fear, which impede the safe learning environment. School users such as students, teachers and parents have the right to a safe, secured and protected environment with the peace of mind that, adequate security measures and procedures are in place to ensure their safety in the school, should a situation arise. Parents as well, should feel at peace with the knowledge that the school environment is secured and that their children and wards are safe in the care of the teachers.

As the fear of violence and crime continues to permeate schools, some security preventive strategies necessary to secure the school environment have been employed in many schools such as the introduction of identity cards for students, school staff and visitors. Others adopt regular locking of all doors and windows, and building of high fence, but despite these efforts, the problem of school security threats persist on increase which indicates that it is necessary to adopt more proactive strategies for daily security improvement to cope with invaders or any other harmful incidence beseeching the public secondary schools in the State. It is on this premise that this study want to examine the extent school emergency safety plans, security training/orientation, recruitment of school security guards, installation of security gadgets, school environmental design, invitation of police patrol, and school-community collaboration as security strategies predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the extent security strategies predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. ascertain the extent security training predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. find out the extent deployment of school security guards predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. examine the extent installation of security gadgets predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

6. To what extent does security training predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
7. What extent does deployment of school security guards predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
8. To what extent does installation of security gadgets predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

3. Security training does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. Deployment of school security guards does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
5. Installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design to determine the extent the independent variable (Security Strategies) and the dependent variable (Safe Learning Environment). The population for this study consisted of 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, specifically 5,833 teachers (i.e., 2,844 male and 2,989 female). A stratified sampling technique was employed to select a sample size of 583 respondents, representing 10% of the total population. The research instrument for this study included

a questionnaire with two sets: Security Strategies Assessment Scale Questionnaire (SSASQ) and Safe Learning Environment Assessment Scale Question (SLEASQ). This instrument has two sections (A and B). Section A gathered demographic information from the respondents, while Section B addressed items related to research questions one through three. The instrument's items were rated on a 4-point Likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point. The instrument was validated, and its reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics, which yielded coefficients of 0.95 and 0.84 for SSASQ and SLEASQ, respectively. The data for this study were primarily collected by the researcher. A total of 583 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, while 564 copies were retrieved and deemed suitable for analysis, resulting in a 97% retrieval rate. Simple regression was used to answer research question one to three research questions, while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses one to three at a 0.05 significance level. Data obtained were processed using Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.00.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the analysed data for the research questions and their corresponding hypothesis are presented in tables as shown below.

Research Question 1: *To what extent does security training predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Extent Security Training Predicts Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.612 ^a	.432	.429	43.2%	Low Extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 1 revealed that, the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .612 and .432 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .429. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 43.2% (.432×100). By implication, the result shows that security training predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 43%.

Research Question 2: *What extent does deployment of school security guards predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Extent Deployment of School Security Guards Predicts Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.421 ^a	.252	.250	25.2%	Low Extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 2 revealed that, the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .421 and .252, respectively, while the adjusted r square is .250. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determination) is 25.2% (.252×100). By implication, the result indicates that, deployment school security guards predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to low extent by 25%.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does installation of security gadgets predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression on the Extent Installation of Security Gadgets Predicts Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of prediction	Decision
1	.337 ^a	.154	.152	15.4%	Very Low Extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 3 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .337 and .154, respectively, while the adjusted r square is 152. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determination) is 15.4% (.154×100). By implication, the result reveals that, installation of security gadgets predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 15%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Security training does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Security Training Significantly Predict Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	2.325	.133		15.182	.000		
1 Security Training	.147	.041	.371	4.651	.112	0.05	Ho ₁ Accepted

a. Dependent Variable: Safe Learning Environment

Table 4 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .371 and 4.651. The p-value of 0.112 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, security training does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: Deployment of school security guards does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Deployment of School Security Guards Significantly Predict Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.736	.117		14.761	.000		
1 Deployment of School Security Guards	.072	.033	.021	.425	.201	0.05	HO ₂ Accepted

a. Dependent Variable: Safe Learning Environment

Table 5 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .021 and .425. The p-value of .201 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, deployment of school security guards does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: Installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 16: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Installation of Security Gadgets Significantly Predict Safe Learning Environment in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error					
(Constant)	1.721	.295		12.341	.000	0.05	H ₀₃ Accepted
1 Installation of Security Gadgets	.216	.124	.224	.152	.139		

a. Dependent Variable: Safe Learning Environment

Table 6 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .224 and .152. The p-value of .139 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed that security training predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent by 43%. Also, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes that security training does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings disagree with Allen and Meyer (2020), Oguntimehin (2021), Iniobong (2022), Owen (2022) whose studies showed that security training predicts safe learning environment in schools. A possible explanation to the findings may be the fact that quite very recently, the government and schools have not seen the need to train members of the public schools in the state on security. Ahmed (2019) opined that training the entire school staff and parents committee have proven to be more efficient than not training at all or training only one or two teachers and expecting them to transfer their knowledge to their colleagues to enhance safe learning environment. Owen (2022) asserted that if school members are not trained on security, it will be difficult for the school to experience safe and conducive environment for learning. This is because the school will lack ideas on how to deal with security challenges.

The second finding of the study showed that deployment of school security guards predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to low extent by 25%. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes that, deployment of school security guards does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings contradict Enang (2019), Mensah, et al (2019), Tillyer, et al. (2020), Bassey (2021), Woodrow and Rich (2021) and Jackson (2022), who found out in their studies that, deployment of school security guards promotes safe learning environment in schools. A possible explanation to the findings may be in fact that school security guards are no longer deployed by the government to schools, and most public schools in the state barely have the means to get security guards to deal with security challenges that the school may face. This is because Oladipo, et al (2019) observed that, the patrol and presence of men of the Nigerian police around schools (especially schools that are prone to attack by crime or disaster) have made life safe to both staff and students. According to the scholars, cultist, bandits, Boko Harams possess, in many cases, more deadly and

functioning weapons that can create an unconducive environment for teaching and learning, but when there is deployment of security guards, it scares these perpetrators away, thereby creating a safe environment for academic activities.

The third finding of this study revealed that installation of security gadgets predicts safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 15%. Also, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes that installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings oppose Okere (2019), Duncanson and Achilles (2019), Williams (2019), Queensl and State School (2021), Gill and Spriggs (2022), and Hassard (2022) whose studies present information that, the installation of security gadgets schools has made a significant impact in promoting safe learning environment in schools. A possible explanation for the findings may be fact that, security gadgets are too expensive for public schools to afford, except they are made available by the government, which they rarely provide. No wonder Jennette (2019) reported that security gadgets if provided in the school can be a watchdog that works 24 hours a day, to make sure that the school compound is safe for learning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, and the discussions on them, it was concluded that school security strategies such as security training, deployment of school security guards, and installation of security gadgets predict safe learning environment in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. School administrators should regularly invite security personnel to their school to lecture and train every member of the on security tips that will help them manage security challenges, in order to ensure safe learning environment.
2. Government should as a matter of urgency deploy trained, qualified and experienced security guards to all public secondary schools within the state to increase the ability to monitor and foil attacks of intruders or criminal agents that would breach peaceful and safe learning environment of the schools.
3. The government should solicit the support of private organisations to assist in the installation of security gadgets in the school, taking it as their corporate social responsibility project, in order to promote safe learning environment. Some of these gadgets should include: CCTV camera, alarms, metal detectors, walkie-talkies, bomb detectors, web security cameras, blind spots cameras, doorbell ringers, siren padlock, motion sensor smart lights, barking dog alarm, GPS trackers, and many others.

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